

Genetics

Inheritance studies for aroma in two aromatic varieties of Pakistan

S. S. Ali, S. J. H. Jafri, M. G. Khan, and M. A. Butt, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Pakistan

Basmati 370 and Basmati 198 are highly aromatic, long-grain indica types. Rice pests have caused severe yield losses during the past few years.

Rice breeders would like to develop cultivars with excellent cooking quality, strong aroma, and resistance to major pests. The inheritance pattern of aroma is being studied systematically to achieve this goal.

We crossed parents Basmati 370 and Basmati 198 with Tetep, a nonaromatic short-grain variety with resistance to many rice insect pests and diseases, during 1990 kharif (monsoon). F_1 and parent seeds were sown during 1991 kharif. F_1 plants were selfed and backcrossed to the aromatic parents to produce BC_1 and F_2 . The aromatic varieties were again crossed with Tetep to produce F_1 seed.

We grew 25 plants each for P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , and F_1 (single 6.3-m row), 100 plants for BC_1 (4 rows), and 200 plants for F_2 (8 rows) in 1992 kharif. A plant-to-plant and row-to-row distance of 23 cm was used.

We evaluated aroma 45 d after transplanting. Two-gram leaf blades from single plants were cut into small pieces, put into test tubes, and soaked in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution for 10 min at 25-30 °C. Samples were classified as aromatic or nonaromatic by smelling.

All F_1 plants were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma in the parents was recessive (see table). Segregating ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic plants was 1:1 in BC_1 and 3:1 in F_2 , further confirming the monogenic inheritance of aroma. Fixation of aroma in early-segregating generations is expected. ■

Behavior of parents, F_1 , BC_1 , and F_2 with regard to aroma 45 d after transplanting.

Designation	Plants (no.)			Ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic		χ^2	P
	Tested	Non-aromatic	Aromatic	Actual	Expected		
Parents							
Basmati 370	25	0	25	0:1	0:1		
Basmati 198	25	0	25	0:1	0:1		
Tetep	25	0	0	1:0	1:0		
F_1							
Basmati 370/Tetep	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
Basmati 198/Tetep	25	25	0	1:0	1:0		
BC_1							
Basmati 370//Basmati 370/Tetep	100	53	47	1:1.1	1:1	0.36	0.50-0.75
Basmati 198//Basmati 198/Tetep	100	52	48	1:1.1	1:1	0.16	0.50-0.75
Total	200	105	95	1:1.1	1:1	0.50	0.25-0.50
F_2							
Basmati 370/Tetep	200	148	52	2.9:1	3:1	0.11	0.50-0.75
Basmati 198/Tetep	200	153	47	3.7:1	3:1	0.24	0.50-0.75
Total	400	301	99	3:1	3:1	0.01	> 0.90

Sensitivity to gibberellic acid (GA_3) of seedlings and endosperms of rice lines with different genes for height

He Zuhua, Shi Cunhai, and Shen Zongtan, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029, China

Five lines carrying different height genes were studied: Mutant T (tall gene Sd_1) and Mutant D (semidwarf gene sd_1), both derived from a heterozygous tall mutant of the cross B_3 /Xin-You-Zhan); Tall Zhen-Shan (recessive tall gene eui) derived from the eui stock; Chao-Ai (recessive dwarf gene $sds_{(w)}$) derived from Xue-He-Ai-Zhao; and dominant dwarf D_{53} . We measured plant elongation 12 d after spraying with 20 ppm GA_3 . Meanwhile, endosperms of the lines were

plated in media with 0.5% soluble starch and 10 ppm GA_3 ; they were stained with I_2 -KI 72 h after culture.

Seedling responses to GA_3 were different among the lines (see table). Based on elongation ratio, Mutant D, Tall Zhen-Shan, and D_{53} were more sensitive to GA_3 than were Mutant T and Chao-Ai. Sensitiveness of the genes for height to GA_3 were $eui > D_{53} > sd_1 > Sd_1 > sds_{(w)}$.

GA_3 induced the endosperms to produce α -amylase, which degraded the starch in the medium. When stained with I_2 -KI, the resulting white spots were larger around the endosperms of Mutant D, Tall Zhen-Shan, and D_{53} , all of which produced more α -amylase than around those of Mutant T and Chao-Ai, which produced less of the enzyme (see figure). Results indicate that genotypes sensitive

Elongation ratios of seedlings treated with GA_3 .

Line	Genotype	Seedling height (cm)		Elongation ratio (%)
		0 ppm GA_3	20 ppm GA_3	
Mutant T	$Sd_1 Sd_1$	19.9	24.6	23.6
Mutant D	$sd_1 sd_1$	14.7	26.0	76.9
Tall Zhen-Shan	$eui eui$	14.5	28.5	96.6
D_{53}	$D_{53} D_{53}$	10.1	18.5	83.2
Chao-Ai	$sds_{(w)} sds_{(w)}$	9.0	10.4	15.6

to GA₃ at the seedling stage also produced endosperm sensitive to GA₃. Endosperm can therefore be used to rapidly identify genotypes that are sensitive to GA₃ with regard to height. ■

Effect of GA₃ on inducing α-amylase in endosperms.

Breeding methods

Identification of stable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for hybrid rice breeding in subhumid tropics

M. Mishra and M. P. Pandey, Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Uttar Pradesh (UP) 263145, India

Environmental factors influence stability of a CMS line. We need to identify suitable lines for developing hybrids adapted to western UP conditions. We evaluated eight CMS lines with wild abortive cytoplasm during 1990 wet season (WS) in a replicated experiment (Table 1).

Analysis of variance indicated significant differences among the CMS lines for seven characters. The lines generally are early flowering, have shorter plant stature, and have more tillers than their respective maintainer lines. CMS lines IR54752 A, IR54753 A, Pragathi, and Pushpa had fertile pollens and long duration and therefore are unstable. Lines IR46829 A, IR54754 A, IR54758 A, and V20 A had complete pollen sterility and did not set any seed in bagged panicles (Table 2). Spikelet fertility was 0.0, 2.7, 11.4, and 17.7%, respectively, for the lines under unbagged conditions. V20 A and IR54758 A had reasonably good seed set under these conditions, indicating better outcrossing

potential, possibly due to their floral traits favoring cross pollination.

Lines possessed early (V20 A) to mid-late (IR46829 A, IR54758 A, and IR54754 A) duration, nonlodging dwarf (V20 A, IR56829 A) or semidwarf (IR54754 A and IR54758 A) plant types, high to moderate tillering capacity, and larger sink size.

Overall comparative performance suggests V20 A and IR54758 A are the most suitable CMS lines because they possess complete stability for pollen sterility, better outcrossing potential under natural conditions, and several desirable plant features under WS conditions of UP. They are being exploited to develop hybrids. ■

Table 1. Analysis of variance of CMS lines for several characters. ^a Western Uttar Pradesh, India, 1990 WS.

Source of variance	Degrees of freedom	Mean square						
		Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Number of effective tillers	Panicle length	Number of spikelets/panicle	Percent fertile spikelets	Percent pollen fertility
Replication	1	18.06	29.17	59.29	20.70	87.59	0.66	91.20
Genotype	7	399.41**	397.14**	45.39*	17.32*	2819.94*	461.41**	854.33**
Error	7	5.49	26.37	8.75	2.31	594.86	19.64	32.52
CV (%)		2.2	5.3	27.7	6.3	13.8	22.8	36.6

* and ** = significant at 5 and 1% level, respectively.